

Continuous enhancement in management, care, and welfare in panthera species in zoological institutions as evidenced by the increase of two survival summary metrics

Lion (*Panthera leo*); Jaguar (*Panthera onca*); Leopard (*Panthera pardus*); Tiger (*Panthera tigris*); Snow leopard (*Panthera uncia*)

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Introduction

This report aims to investigate trends in life expectancy and lifespan equality in the five *Panthera* species under human care from the mid-1800s to 2023 in zoological institutions and to contextualise these trends in relation to contemporary *ex situ* animal management practices.

The last decades (i.e., since the 1990s) revealed that *ex situ* measures have become more and more relevant in species conservation because of the accelerating loss of habitats and animal species (Ceballos et al. 2015; IUCN SSC 2023). Even charismatic species like African wild ass (*Equus africanus*) or Philippine spotted deer (*Rusa alfredi*) may be lost without *ex situ* assurance populations in zoological institutions. The major role of zoos and aquariums (referred as “zoological institutions” hereafter) in *ex situ* conservation efforts for more and more species comes with a growing responsibility and an increased need for goal-oriented and scientifically-evaluated husbandry and population management. To play a relevant role in the frame of the One Plan Approach (Byers et al. 2013) for *Panthera* species conservation, zoological institutions need to define the key features of population management under excellent husbandry conditions for these species. This requires the objective analysis of previous and present management practices. This report is a first step towards closing the gap between experience-based expertise and societal debates about *Panthera* species in captivity by analysing populations survival parameters to evaluate husbandry success, using objective data sets.

Historically, zoological institutions have shifted their role from museums with living animal collections to institutions where conservation is at the centre of their focus, therefore, dedicating significant time, energy, resources, and research to animal welfare (see Beer et al. 2023 and Vincelette 2024 for review). Individual institutions do not represent isolated entities, but they are linked in regional, continental and global organisations, which also set standards in terms of husbandry, collection plans and population management, and who exert control about adherence to commonly decided policies and practices via accreditation programs (Hutchins and Smith 2003; Hutchins et al. 2016). Although problematic establishments still exist, and welfare standards continue to evolve, accredited zoological institutions are transforming, or already have completely transformed, into institutions serving conservation, education, and research activities (Coe 1996; Grow et al. 2024).

Animal welfare in zoological institutions is also paramount for broader conservation goals in order to ensure behaviourally competent, disease-free, and genetically suitable individuals. Poor welfare can lead to distress, compromised immune function, behavioural inflexibility, reduced breeding success, and decreased survival rates (Wingfield and Sapolsky 2003; Morgan and Tromborg 2007; Walker et al. 2012). Furthermore, observing healthy animals engaging in natural behaviours is essential for gathering valuable insights into the biology of their counterparts in the wild and for educating the public about their natural habits (Fernandez et al. 2009).

Despite ethical concerns regarding the care and welfare of animals under human care, widespread public interest remains in visiting zoos and aquariums. Indeed, people seek to reconnect with nature and experience positive emotions through interactions with animals, and conservation of species has indirect values to society (MacNally et al. 2024). Over the recent decades, this public has also become more interested in, and aware of, the welfare of zoo animals. Changes in societies’ perception of animals – wild or domestic – have been an important driver for this transformation. This shift is exemplified by the establishment of non-governmental organisations dedicated to protecting wildlife

from human activities and by various domestic and global legislations enacted throughout the 20th century to govern the treatment of captive big cats. A prevailing argument against zoological institutions posits that animals under human care experience shorter life expectancies than their wild counterparts, leading to claims that zoological institutions offer substandard living conditions for their animals (e.g., in elephants, Clubb et al. 2008; Atkinson and Lindsay 2022). Accredited zoological institutions recognize the importance of animal welfare and put significant effort into animal welfare research and implementation.

In this study, big cats correspond to the five species belonging to the genus *Panthera*: the **lion** (*P. leo*), **jaguar** (*P. onca*), **leopard** (*P. pardus*), **tiger** (*P. tigris*) and **snow leopard** (*P. uncia*). Four of these species are considered **Threatened** on the Red List of Threatened Species, by the International Union for Conservation for Nature (IUCN 2023), while the jaguar is considered as **Near Threatened**. Moreover, the global population size in the wild is decreasing for the five species, underscoring the urgency of conservation efforts for them. Furthermore, in November 2023, the IUCN Species Survival Commission (SSC) acknowledged “*the significant contributions that botanical gardens, aquariums, and zoos can, and do, bring to conserving wild animals, fungi and plants*” (IUCN SSC 2023). Banning species from accredited zoological institutions may represent missed opportunities to **(i)** acquire species-specific knowledge to support conservation efforts (Loh et al. 2018; Conde et al. 2019), **(ii)** care for confiscated animals or serve as a temporary home for rescued ones (IUCN SSC, 2023), **(iii)** maintain assurance populations that help preserve species and their genetic diversity until threats in the wild are abated, to allow potential reintroduction into the wild (Ballou et al. 2010), and **(iv)** promoting public engagement and behaviour change through education (McNally et al. 2024).

Survival-related metrics are commonly used as a proxy of population-level welfare as happier and healthier individuals have been reported to live longer (Diener and Chan 2011; Weiss et al. 2011; Walker et al. 2012). Here, we studied the change in two key survival summary metrics – proved to be a reliable proxy of population welfare in human and non-human animals (Colchero et al. 2016, 2021; Aburto et al. 2020; Tidière et al. 2023) – for the five *Panthera* species living in zoological institutions between 1874 and 2023. **Our results confirmed the progressive enhancement of the conditions of life provided to the five species of big cats examined here and housed in zoological institutions.** The average life expectancy at birth of females and males of the five species has increased by 5.4 years in the past century. This improvement is particularly impressive for the **tigers**, which had a life expectancy of approximately 5.5 years at the beginning of the 20th century, while individuals born in zoological institutions today have a life expectancy of around 13.0 years, a 2.4-fold improvement in 100 years. Next, we reviewed scientific literature detailing the various efforts made by modern zoological institutions to improve the care and welfare of big cats under their care, to contextualise the observed survival improvements. Criticisms of animals under human care are relatively recent, while literature reviews and expert knowledge show that accredited zoological institutions began focusing on husbandry and welfare as early as the beginning of the 20th century (see Young 2003; Hosey et al. 2020; Vincelette 2024). These efforts underscore the proactive behaviour of accredited zoological institutions in constantly improving their management practices striving to provide for the wellbeing of big cats.

This research contributes to the ongoing discourse on animal welfare in zoological institutions and may inform future policy decisions. It also underscores the importance of biology-informed husbandry, resource investment and scientific research in enhancing the lives of animals in zoological institutions.

I. Study of population welfare based on survival parameters for big cats in zoological institutions between 1874 and 2023

We conducted a sex-specific temporal analysis of survival of the five *Panthera* species in zoological institutions worldwide since 1874. We estimated changes in population welfare by defining two summary metrics related to the distribution of age at death in the population: **life expectancy** and **lifespan equality** (see Box 1). The combination of these two metrics has been shown as a measure of a population's welfare in both in humans and non-human animals (Colchero et al. 2016; Tidière et al. 2023, see Box 1 for more details).

Box 1. Life Expectancy & Lifespan Equality: an indicator of societal and wellbeing improvements in human populations.

What is Life Expectancy?

It is a statistical measure of the average time an organism is expected to live, based on the year of its birth, current age, and other demographic factors like sex. The life expectancy is given in units of time (e.g., years).

What is Lifespan Equality?

This metric encompasses two components: (1) how similar are lifespans of individuals from a given population: homogeneous across ages or concentrated; and (2) whether the probability of death in this population is higher early or late in life. Therefore, in a population, the higher the concentration of deaths at older ages, the higher the equality. The lifespan equality is comparable to the inverse of the coefficient of variation of age at death in the population, and is a metric without units nor boundaries. It is not used on its own but for comparison.

Why are these measures an indicator of wellbeing in a population?

Research in animals and humans has shown that increases in the quality of the surrounding environment, and then indirectly in welfare, are associated with higher survival rates and longer lifespans through direct mechanisms (i.e., interventions directly preventing deaths; [NHTSA](#)) and indirect mechanisms (i.e., the long-lasting cumulative effects of factors degrading or improving health conditions, such as nutrition, medical care, and happiness; Mishra 2016). Mortality rates (and thus survival) are common indicators of wellbeing used in humans and other species (Walker et al. 2012; Aburto et al. 2020). Indeed, **happier and healthier individuals live longer** (Diener and Chan 2011; Weiss et al. 2011; Walker et al. 2012).

What can the relationship between life expectancy and lifespan equality tell us about changes in wellbeing in a population?

Studies have found that, in humans, life expectancy and lifespan equality are highest in modern industrialised societies due to the concentration of deaths at old ages and a steep reduction in infant and juvenile mortality. Both measures are lower in non-industrialised populations, due to higher mortality at young ages and higher environmental causes of mortality (Colchero et al. 2016; Tidière et al. 2023). The increase in life expectancy and lifespan equality in tandem across time reflects improvements in societal welfare across different human populations, and the decrease of one or both is directly related to a degradation in the population conditions of life (Aburto and Beltrán-Sánchez 2019). Likewise, studies on non-human primates (Colchero et al. 2021) and four marine mammal species (Tidière et al. 2023) have shown that the same pattern occurs when comparing wild populations and animals living in zoological institutions. While changes in this indicator reflect the changes in terms of conditions of life and welfare of a population, it cannot be used to assess the welfare at the individual level.

Estimation of the life expectancy and lifespan equality

Records were obtained from the Zoological Information Management System (ZIMS) managed by Species360, a non-profit organisation with over 1,300 current members all around the world, including zoos, aquariums, rescue centres, and wildlife sanctuaries (Species360 2023). Records were extracted from the *Husbandry Module* of ZIMS and included dates of birth and death (when applicable) of all sexed individuals belonging the genus *Panthera* living in zoological institutions from the early 1800s to December 4th, 2023 (Data Use Agreement #95155). The **lion** (*P. leo*), **jaguar** (*P. onca*), **leopard** (*P. pardus*), **tiger** (*P. tigris*) and **snow leopard** (*P. uncia*) were retained for the study because the database contained at least 100 individuals per sex for each period and species, to ensure unbiased mortality estimates and minimise uncertainty (Colchero and Clark 2012; see Tidière et al. 2023 for more details on the methods).

For each sex and each species, the individuals were divided into six (eight for the **tiger**) different groups corresponding to time periods of at least 15 years (see Figure 1). To define mortality patterns, we fitted a Siler mortality model (Siler 1979) using Bayesian survival trajectory analysis (BaSTA) package (Colchero and Clark 2012; Colchero et al. 2012) in R (R Core Team 2023). From the patterns of sex- and age-specific mortality, we defined two means of summary statistics: the **life expectancy** and the **lifespan equality** (see Box 1 and Tidière et al. 2023 for more details on the methods).

Figure 1. Increase in life expectancy and lifespan equality across time for females and males of the five *Panthera* species in zoological institutions from 1874 to 2023. The markers indicate the mean values obtained per sex, period, and species, while the line represents the species-specific trend.

Enhanced life expectancy and lifespan equality of *Panthera* species in zoological institutions over time

Our results show a global and progressive increase of the two-summary metrics for both sexes and the five species between 1874 and 2023 (Figure 1). During the studied period, life expectancy at birth has increased by 5.4 years on average (corresponding to a factor of 1.8) for males and females of the five species, ranging from an increase of 3.2 years for the **leopard** to 7.5 years for **tiger** females. For example, the life expectancy at birth of a female **tiger** born in a zoological institution before 1952 was 5.50 ± 0.71 years ($n=207$ individuals) but changed to 13.00 ± 0.29 years ($n=1,912$ individuals, 2.4-fold increase, Table 1) in the 2013-2023 period. These findings confirm the results obtained in a previous study highlighting the general increase of survival and longevity metrics for many carnivorous species, including the five big cats, in zoological institutions (Roller et al. 2021). Similarly, lifespan equality improved for both females and males of the four species between 1874 and 2023, with an increase of 0.723 on average, ranging from 0.245 for **lion** males to 1.134 for **tiger** females.

Our results demonstrate an overall improvement on a population level in parameters related to survival. However, these results do not provide a direct indicator of individuals' welfare within those populations. Nevertheless, this population-level welfare indicator can still both provide evidence of progress already made, as well as further opportunities for continuous improvement in animal welfare.

Table 1. Summary of average life expectancy at birth changes between the earliest and latest periods.

Species	Sex	Compared periods	Increase in years	Factor of increase
Lion <i>Panthera leo</i>	Females	1874-1972 vs. 2013-2023	6.0	1.9
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	1.7	1.2
	Males	1874-1972 vs. 2013-2023	4.7	1.7
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	1.6	1.2
Jaguar <i>Panthera onca</i>	Females	1875-1972 vs. 2013-2023	5.0	1.5
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	0.4	1.0
	Males	1875-1971 vs. 2013-2023	5.8	1.5
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	2.3	1.2
Leopard <i>Panthera pardus</i>	Females	1874-1971 vs. 2013-2023	3.2	1.3
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	0.0	1.0
	Males	1874-1971 vs. 2013-2023	3.2	1.3
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	0.0	1.0
Tiger <i>Panthera tigris</i>	Females	1874-1951 vs. 2013-2023	7.5	2.4
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	0.4	1.0
	Males	1874-1951 vs. 2013-2023	6.9	2.2
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	0.7	1.1
Snow leopard <i>Panthera uncia</i>	Females	1903-1971 vs. 2013-2023	6.2	2.4
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	0.4	1.0
	Males	1903-1971 vs. 2013-2023	6.2	2.5
		2003-2012 vs. 2013-2023	0.4	1.0

II. Population survival improvement is tied to the continuous advances made by accredited zoological institutions

The rise in life expectancy and lifespan equality of big cats over time can be attributed to various factors, many of which may have interacted synergistically. Notably transitioning zoological institutions from menageries to accredited institutions committed to animal conservation and welfare, research, and public education, underscores the steady improvement in survival metrics for *Panthera* species. In this section, we examine the diverse factors that have positively influenced the survival and longevity of big cats in zoological institutions, drawing support from scientific literature and accumulated knowledge and experience of experts of these species.

Change in public perception and legislation

Our perception of big cats has undergone a significant transformation over the past two centuries. Historically seen mainly as formidable and fearsome wild creatures, they are now fascinating in a nuanced and holistic manner. This shift is largely attributed to documentaries, research studies, and media coverage emphasising the complex needs of *Panthera* species, such as their extensive territorial requirements, natural behaviours, and mental health. Furthermore, big cats have become emblematic of the adverse effects of human–wildlife conflicts (Woodroffe 2000; Balme et al. 2009; Goodrich 2010; Blackburn et al. 2016; IUCN 2023), with 75% of the world’s felid species being affected by conflict-related killing (WWF 2022; Panthera and WWF).

Zoological institutions themselves have become advocates for animal rights, as evidenced by initiatives like the “Roadmap to Closing Captive Tiger Facilities of Concern” (Four Paws et al. 2023) and organisations such as the Big Cat Sanctuary Alliance (BCSA) who have adapted their position accordingly, stating that they oppose the keeping of big cats in all non-accredited zoological institutions but take no position on the display of wild big cats in (AZA-)accredited institutions (Big Cat Sanctuary Alliance 2024). As our understanding of the biology and needs of big cats deepens, we witness corresponding improvements in their welfare and survival, both at the population and individual level.

Establishment of international organisations

Changes in perception of big cats are exemplified by the establishment of non-governmental organisations dedicated to protecting wildlife from human activities. For instance, the IUCN spearheaded in 1973 an agreement amongst more than 80 Parties to regulate wildlife trade. This agreement resulted in the establishment of the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), which took effect in 1975. This agreement, placing all *Panthera* species under CITES Appendix I (since 1975, **lions** since 1977), restricts international trade to protect wild populations. Consequently, zoological institutions could no longer source wild-born individuals, which spearheaded the initiation of collaborative breeding programs and meta-population management to obtain self-sustainable populations in zoological institutions. This prompted institutions to focus on expert exchanges, and cooperation, to obtain self-sustainable, demographically stable, and genetically diverse populations. These regulatory changes in animal transfers and wild

capture, particularly impactful in the 1980s, likely spurred comprehensive efforts to improve big cats' physical health and survival.

Regulation through laws and policies

Various legislations were enacted both domestically and globally to govern the treatment of captive big cats throughout the 20th century. Notably, the USA Animal Welfare Act of 1966 (AWA) established minimum standards for the treatment of animals in research, teaching, exhibition, transport, and by dealers. Similarly, European nations introduced their own regulations, such as the Danish Act for Animal Welfare in 1916 and the UK Zoo Licensing Act of 1981, before the European Union implemented Directive 1999/22/EC. This European directive on the housing of wild animals in zoos, settles the minimally acceptable standards for zoological institutions such as “*accomodat[ing] their animals under conditions that satisfy the biological and conservation requirements of the individual species*”. However, determining these minimum standards remains challenging, leading to variations between countries.

In 2017, the Big Cat Sanctuary Alliance (BCSA) was created to eliminate private ownership and the commercial exploitation of wild cats in the USA. One significant step toward achieving BCSA's mission was the signing of the Big Cat Public Safety Act – a federal level solution to the dangerous and cruel practices associated with the private ownership of big cats and direct contact activities like cub petting – into law in the USA in 2022.

These regulations embody the collective concern of zoo professionals, governmental agencies, and the public for the humane and enhanced care of *ex situ* big cats. Therefore, the progressive implementation of regulations throughout the 20th century has contributed to the global advancement of care and management practices in accredited zoological institutions, resulting in the observed reduced mortality rates among managed big cats.

Professionalisation and organisation

Professionalisation

Accredited zoological institutions have undergone significant transformation, particularly through the professionalisation of their staff. Notably, biologists and veterinarians are now permanently employed and have advanced their expertise in wildlife biology and medicine through education and research (Fowler 1977, 2006; and detailed in the *Veterinary medicine and health care* section). Furthermore, the establishment of specialised training programs, like the first French school for zookeepers opening in the 1990s (Houssaye F., Pers. Comm.), illustrates this commitment to professional development. In some countries, such as in Denmark, each government-approved zoological institution must have at least one zoologist or similarly qualified expert to offer high-level advice on public education, data management, breeding programs, and overall development (Ministeriet for Fødevarer, Landbrug og Fiskeri 2015).

Data and technology use in animal management

Data-based management

The professionalisation of zoological institutions has been accompanied by the systematic enhancement of data recording efforts. Historically, record-keeping practices were inconsistent, with only notable animals, such as those that contributed to pedigrees or survived to an arbitrary age, being documented (e.g., Scherer et al. 2024). This selective recording often excluded stillborn individuals or those dying young, leading to underestimation of mortality rates in earlier records. By the 1980s, records became reasonably accurate and comprehensive. Data entered post-2000 is considered high-quality, reflecting significant improvements in record-keeping standards. For instance, the pedigree quality of **lions** in European Association of Zoos and Aquariums (EAZA) substantially declines for records older than 2000, especially those pre-dating 1990, indicating that many historical litters were unrecorded or lost. This results in a paucity of data from those periods compared to current records and only strengthens the argument of the observed survival improvements in Figure 1. Also, it is important to keep in mind that each sub-species is not equally represented in zoological institutions, with the Amur **leopard** (*P. p. orientalis*) dominating **leopard** data, the Transvaal **lion** (*P. l. krugeri*) dominating **lion** data, and the Amur **tiger** (*P. t. altaica*) and Sumatran **tiger** (*P. t. sumatrae*) dominating **tiger** data.

One pivotal development in this regard was the establishment of the non-profit organisation Species360 (formerly the International Species Information System) in 1974 (Seal et al. 1976; Earnhardt et al. 1995; Flesness 2003). The Zoological Information Management System (ZIMS), from Species360, serves as a comprehensive repository for individual animal data pertaining to husbandry, medical, welfare and population management, with some records dating back to the early 1800s. This systematic documentation enables zoological institutions to monitor the daily health and welfare of their animals, facilitating age-, sex-, and species-specific analyses. These data inform evidence-based husbandry practices and management decisions and are vital for scientific research, enhancing our understanding of species. The accumulation and analysis of standardised data continues to be used to refine husbandry practices (Earnhardt et al. 1995; Che-Castaldo et al. 2019) and ultimately enhances the survival and welfare of big cats living in human care.

Technology for animal monitoring

In the 1970s and 80s, camera technology was first introduced in the USA to monitor young animals, facilitating timely interventions. This advancement, now used in many institutions in the world, enhanced understanding of litter sizes, stillbirth occurrences and maternal behaviour such as stillborn consumption. By the early 1990s, camera monitoring became routine, offering detailed observations of animal behaviour and environmental interactions. This technology provides key information for assessing animal preferences and informing management practices to reduce stress. Overnight monitoring, crucial when direct supervision is not feasible, ensures day-time management strategies which positively influence nocturnal behaviour, reducing stereotypical actions and enhancing welfare.

Organisation into Regional Associations

Promoting international collaborations

Along the 20th century, zoological institutions structured themselves into different regional associations, to organise the cooperation between them. Many associations are existing today at different levels (world, continent, regional, national, etc...), such as:

- AZA: (American) Association of Zoo and Aquariums (1924)
- WAZA: World Association of Zoos and Aquariums (1935)
- EAZA: European Association of Zoos and Aquaria (1985)
- PAAZA: Pan-African Association of Zoo and Aquaria (1989)
- CZAI: The Central Zoo Authority of India (1989)
- ALPZA: Latin American Zoo and Aquarium Association (1990)
- SEAZA: SouthEast Asian Zoos and Aquariums Association (1990)
- ZAA: Zoo and Aquarium Association Australasia (1990)

These associations enhance the exchanges between institutions, establish accreditation protocols that define acceptable standards of animal care and welfare within their region, and promote the different goals of the accredited zoological institutions (i.e., education, research, and conservation). While each regional association developed their own Felid Taxon Advisory Group (TAG), the AZA initiated the first one in 1990 (Tilson et al. 2016). These regional associations encourage and promote high standards for the husbandry of zoo and aquarium animals. For instance, some of the zoo and aquarium regional associations (e.g., AZA and EAZA) have organized advisors and scientific groups (e.g., focusing on nutrition, welfare, behaviour, population biology) to support population management programs.

Definition of animal care standards

One way to ensure and promote high husbandry standards is through the implementation of various animal care standards. The progressive increase in survivorship of big cats in zoological institutions over the last century can be attributed to improved zoo management practices. These changes have been driven by guidelines and care manuals published by regional zoo associations, tailored to better meet the needs of managed big cats by serving as invaluable resources for caretakers and zoological institutions, facilitating continuous improvements in the living conditions of big cats. The development of these guidelines represents decades of collective experience and scientific insights, establishing high standards for the husbandry of *Panthera* species. They support constant evidence-based evolution of accredited zoos approaches.

For instance, **lions** have been managed under human care for over a century, and it was discovered that isolating pregnant females for delivery improves breeding success. This extensive experience has made **lions** relatively easy to breed in various settings, and are today included in the guidelines for this species (e.g., AZA Lion Survival Plan 2012). The guidelines delineate expectations for member institutions to ensure optimal welfare and expertise. They also consider the varying needs, popularity, and size differences between subspecies (e.g., Tidière et al. 2021).

Meta-population management

Given the endangered status of big cats and the threats facing wild populations, conserving them through captive populations is imperative. The focus is on maintaining demographically stable and genetically diverse populations compensating for losses due to genetic drift and inbreeding (Seal and Foose 1983; WAZA website), crucial for future potential reintroduction efforts if required, while upholding high standards of animal welfare (Boer 1991). Species with a WAZA studbook are expected to have longer lifespans in zoological institutions, likely due to the increased attention and improved husbandry practices associated with studbook management. The management via studbooks is therefore recommended as part of the conservation strategy for the **northern lion** (*Panthera leo leo*) (Funston et al. 2023). Over the past 35 years, collaboration among zoological institutions has intensified to enhance species management, focusing on improving breeding outcomes and ensuring future survival.

Population management programs

Following the establishment of CITES regulations, thereby limiting the import of wild caught animals, regional associations and zoological institutions have spearheaded initiatives to establish collaborative management plans and breeding programs. The breeding programs manage small populations within zoological institutions as part of a larger collective – a meta-population – with the aim to maintain self-sustainable, demographically stable, and genetically diverse populations containing animals with good welfare. Institutions that house a particular species collaborate in *ex situ* breeding programs aimed at managing small populations within zoological institutions as part of a larger collective encompassing all zoo animals, operating at regional and/or global scales. These breeding programs are an integral part of the One Plan Approach as defined by the IUCN, which aims to unite *in situ* and *ex situ* actions to develop relevant conservation strategies that mitigate the biodiversity crisis (Byers et al. 2013). Indeed, regional breeding programs like the Species Survival Plan (SSP) in North America, the EAZA Ex-situ Programme (EEP, formerly named European Endangered species Programme) within the EAZA region, or the Species Management Program (SMP) in the Australasia, have been instrumental in conserving genetically diverse captive populations over the long term. A basic concept of these breeding programs is that they are self-sustainable without import of individuals from natural habitats. This is done by preventing individuals from being inbred, since they might suffer from reduced reproductive and survival parameters (Ballou et al. 2010), preventing cross breeding subspecies to avoid hybrids and by preserving as much genetic diversity from founders as possible (Seal and Foose 1983). The establishment of international and regional studbooks in the 1960s underscores the commitment to coordinated breeding efforts (Blomqvist 1995; Christie 2010; Tilson et al. 2016). For example, the international studbook for **snow leopards** was established at Helsinki Zoo in 1976, with a captive population of 53 founders (Blomqvist 1995).

For nearly two decades, the WAZA “*strongly recommends that all breeding programmes should be based on sound science and management using the latest available knowledge on population management, reproductive biology, genetics, animal behaviour, nutrition, veterinary care and husbandry standards*” (WAZA 2005, and see WAZA 2027). These breeding programs are actually an integral part of the One Plan Approach defined by the IUCN, aiming to consider *in situ* and *ex situ*

actions together to develop relevant conservation strategies working at slowing down the biodiversity crisis (Byers et al. 2013).

Juvenile survival and hand-raising

Between the 1950s and 1980s, hand-raising of mammals was common practice in zoological institutions to enhance survival rates by providing intensive veterinary care. This practice significantly influenced animals' adaptation to human contact. However, hand-raising has also been linked to social inadaptation with conspecifics and poor breeding behaviour for adult big cats (Simonsen K.S., Pers. Comm., Biddle 2022). Consequently, since the 1990s, a shift towards mother-rearing has been recommended despite potential higher cub mortality rates, as it enhances social and reproductive capacities in adulthood. Current practices minimise human interaction and focus on rearing multiple animals together to promote natural socialisation. Additionally, providing offspring with access to experienced mothers has shown to enhance their skills significantly. This evolution in juvenile care practices has likely contributed to a significant decrease in cub mortality rates for the five *Panthera* species managed under human care over recent decades (Blomqvist 1995; Roller et al. 2021).

Veterinary medicine and health care

Veterinary medicine progresses closely following the development of human medicine, often incorporating knowledge, tools and treatments used in human health care (Gutierrez et al. 2023). The steady enhancement of survival metrics among big cats in modern zoological settings presented in this report underscores the dynamic nature of the continuous progress made in management and veterinary practices of big cats in zoological institutions.

Veterinarians in zoological institutions

Throughout history, zoo veterinarians have played a pivotal role in the care of zoo animals. The profession traces back to the appointment of the first zoo veterinarian in the UK in 1829, followed by the establishment of similar roles in the USA from the early 1900s. By the 1970s, most zoological institutions housing big cats typically employed full-time veterinarians. In some instances, zoo directors also held veterinary qualifications, although they may not have practised veterinary medicine while serving in administrative roles. As early as 1902, the New York Zoological Society aimed to formalise veterinary care by establishing a permanent medical department (Osborn 1903). This initiative aimed to advance understanding of wildlife health in captivity, identify disease causes, and develop preventive measures. This professionalisation has revolutionised disease prevention and treatment in captive settings, as well as daily care, improving survival rates among zoo inhabitants. Institutional husbandry experience and retaining knowledge through staff turnovers has been shown to be critical to ensure optimal reproduction and survival of individuals (Saunders et al. 2014).

Organisation and professionalisation

The evolution of zoo veterinary advisory groups has been ongoing for nearly 50 years growing in capacity and expertise over time. Specialised organisations like the American College of Zoological

Medicine (ACZM) or the European College of Zoological Medicine (ECZM) have further professionalised the field since the 1980s. These bodies offer formal training and certification for zoo veterinarians, shaping the present and future of zoo animal medicine. Key developments to improve breeding success and long-term viability include the establishment of professional bodies such as the American Association of Zoo Veterinarians (AAZV) in 1946 and the British Veterinary Zoological Society (BVZS) in 1961 (see Fowler 1977 for more details). The World Association of Wildlife Veterinarians (WAWV) emerged from the World Veterinary Association in 1991, followed by the formation of the European Association of Zoo and Wildlife Veterinarians (EAZWV) in 1996.

These associations facilitate knowledge exchange and provide training for future zoo veterinarians. Notably, university-based training programs in zoo animal medicine were non-existent globally until 1968. Zoo veterinarians, in close collaboration with biologists, have been instrumental in setting standards for the care of wildlife, including enclosure and pool sizes, environmental conditions, and dietary requirements. Their involvement in accreditation programs, such as the AZA accreditation, underscores their commitment to ensuring the humane treatment of animals and compliance with regulatory standards, including the USA Federal Animal Welfare Act (Schroeder 1976). Finally, platforms like the module *ZIMS for Medical* from Species360 are used by veterinarians to exchange diagnostic insights among a network of peers, facilitating collaborative problem-solving and knowledge-sharing within the profession. This exemplifies the modern approach to veterinary care in zoological settings, emphasising collaboration and access to collective expertise.

Veterinary research

Since the 1970s, there has been a notable advancement in veterinary care research, marked by the creation of the *Journal of Zoo Animal Medicine* in 1970. Scientific papers on this matter appear in the literature from the 1960s. The number of papers published by zoological institutions has steadily increased since then (Loh et al. 2018; Hvilsom et al. 2020; Kögler et al. 2020).

More specifically, for the *Panthera* species there has been an increased focus on the primary causes of death, such as identifying and managing chronic kidney disease (CKD) often associated with ageing, through dietary adaptations. For instance, CKD is a contributing factor in nearly 40% of adult and geriatric **snow leopard** deaths in zoological institutions (Womble et al. 2021), which is a clear consequence of more individuals surviving to the age where CKD manifests itself. Having a higher proportion of older animals in zoological institutions nowadays naturally leads to an increased prevalence of these conditions. In general, the advancements in zoo medicine have led to increased survival rates and longer lifespans in big cats, also resulting in a rise in age-related diseases such as cancer (Lombard and Witte 1959; Womble et al. 2021; Vincze et al. 2022). Therefore, regular monitoring of kidney values and ultrasound examinations are now integral to their health management to improve and secure their survival.

Training to facilitate medical procedures

With roots in the early 20th century, animal training has seen renewed interest among veterinarians for its role in promoting regular health assessments and minimising stress during interventions. Since the 1960s, zoological institutions have increasingly adopted training big cats for medical procedures, particularly through operant conditioning techniques. Over the past two decades, these practices have

substantially expanded non-invasive health monitoring capabilities. The 2010s marked a significant rise in training applications for medical procedures like blood draws and ultrasounds, minimising the need for anaesthesia. For example, training for medical procedures enable pregnancy monitoring via transabdominal ultrasound with minimal stress, eliminating the psychological and physiological impacts of anaesthesia (Broder et al. 2008). Training animals in general also has facilitated animal transport events as it can reduce the need and risk related to the use of anaesthesia. These voluntary trainings facilitate early health issue detection, enabling timely medical intervention, reducing immobilisation risks and improving treatment outcomes, thereby contributing to the enhanced survival and longevity of animals under human care.

Medical practices

The advent of modern drugs since the 1980s has greatly improved disease prevention and treatment, further enhancing the health and wellbeing of captive big cats. The implementation of quarantine and vaccination protocols further reduced mortality rates, alongside improvements in anaesthesia and antibiotic treatments. Emphasis on enclosure cleanliness, sanitation, and disinfection prevents the spread of pathogens like microorganisms and parasites. For example, enclosures, service areas, and quarantine facilities are now equipped with footbaths for disinfection. Moreover, a comprehensive pest management program, compliant with local laws, helps eliminate disease sources from feral mammals, rodents, birds, and insects. This strategy prevents the transmission of diseases such as rabies, feline viral diseases, yersiniosis, leptospirosis, salmonellosis, toxoplasmosis, and feline infectious peritonitis. These changes in medical practices further ensure the health and longevity of the big cats in zoological institutions.

Nutrition

As a fundamental aspect of animal management, nutrition is essential for growth, disease prevention, reproduction, and longevity (Dierenfeld 1997). Proper feeding of wild animals under human care requires both applied nutritional sciences and husbandry skills. It is therefore important for conservation if we aim to reintroduce captive-born and raised felids into their natural habitats (Reeves et al. 2020) as it influences for example the development of the skulls and mandible shape of big cats (Siciliano-Martina et al. 2021; Cooper et al. 2023).

Historically, zoo animals have faced various health issues, including under- and over-nourishment, and diet-related chronic diseases such as obesity and diabetes, that modern dietary practices focus on avoiding (Dierenfeld 1997). The nutrition of *Panthera* species in zoological institutions has improved significantly over the past century, being influenced by the establishment of organisations like the Nutrition Advisory Group in AZA (1994) and the European Zoo Nutrition Group in EAZA (1999). These organisations, along with recommendations from regional associations and evolving practices in zoological institutions, have driven nutritional advancements for captive animals over the last 50 years.

Significant improvements have resulted from incorporating research on the feeding ecology of free-ranging populations into the diets of their captive counterparts. Moreover, changes have occurred not

only in the *what* is provided to big cats but also in the *how*, along with evolving perceptions and definitions of a healthy body weight.

Change in diet

In the early 1900s, big cats in zoological institutions were primarily fed a processed meat-only diet, which was deficient in certain essential nutrients. This led to numerous health issues, including metabolic bone disease. In 1889, Dr. John Bland-Sutton, a prominent London surgeon, identified the diet as the cause regarding fatal rickets in **lion** cubs at the London Zoo, and recommended changes in their diet, resulting in reversing rickets and allowing the cubs to survive and thrive. Thirty years later, the definitive role of calcium, phosphate and vitamin D in prevention and therapy of rickets was elucidated (Park 1923; Rajakumar 2003; Chesney and Hedberg 2010).

Significant advancements occurred in the mid-20th century introducing diets with calculated nutrient concentrations tailored to specific animal groups (Ratcliffe 1966). This change drastically improved survival rates, reducing the overall annual mortality of mammals and birds from 20% to 10% (Wackernagel 1966). Since then, the feeding of carnivores in zoological institutions typically either focuses on processed meat supplemented during processing with essential nutrients, on the feeding of whole meat (with or without bone) treated with supplements, or on the feeding of whole carcasses (that generally represent a complete diet for carnivores) (Kleinlugtenbelt et al. 2023b). Whereas all three diet types deliver the classic nutrients in appropriate amounts, they vary distinctively in their behavioural value. Additionally, physical effects of hard tissue like bone for oral health (Fitch and Fagan 1982) and of indigestible or difficult-to-digest components for gut health (Depauw et al. 2013) have been suggested, which means that the diet types should provide benefits in increasing order. From 2010 onwards, there was a move towards individualised diets tailored to the specific needs of each individual animal, based on criteria such as its species, age, weight, sex, and reproductive status (e.g., gestation, lactation). Other efforts include the development of the Felid Faecal Scoring System in 2014 advancing the direct monitoring and management of the health of felids by assessing the diet effectiveness, detecting health issues earlier, and making the necessary nutritional adjustments (Tilson et al. 2016).

Overall, these dietary improvements have significantly enhanced the health and welfare of captive big cats, contributing to better health outcomes and by that longevity. Diet practices are continuously refined by accredited zoological institutions, to offer species-appropriate diets.

Change in feeding method

As previously mentioned, not only *what* an animal is fed, but also *how* they are fed will influence their overall health and wellbeing. The evolution of feeding practices in zoological institutions may have enhanced the health and welfare of big cats by promoting species-specific behaviours and improving survival rates. Since the 1990s, food access has been made more challenging to promote natural foraging behaviours, including scatter feeding and feeding at heights to mimic natural patterns and encourage stimulation. For example, the installation of poles in their enclosure requires **tigers** to climb and use their body weight to reach the food (Law and Kitchener 2020), which positively impacts skeletal development and strength (Cooper et al. 2023). These methods also promote exercise and

dental health, crucial for preventing cardiovascular diseases, though they still remain underutilised (Kleinlugtenbelt et al. 2023a).

Diverse feeding methods introduced by Law et al. (1997) exemplify efforts to enhance the psychological and physical health of zoo animals. In Switzerland, legislation mandates that *Panthera* species exert effort to obtain food, promoting naturalistic feeding behaviours and enhancing welfare (Clauss M., Pers. Comm.). For instance, carcass feeding addresses specific dietary requirements, and also supports natural feeding behaviours such as caching and feast/fast cycles, promoting physical and psychological health (Gilbert-Norton et al. 2009). Defined by the AZA Nutrition Scientific Advisory Group, whole carcass feeding involves offering intact animals complete with entrails, fur, and/or feathers, or bodies with hide and viscera removed, and is adapted to species-specific needs. Moreover, the use of fasting days is common practice in zoo large carnivore husbandry, even though the reasons for this may not necessarily be to mimic the natural pattern of gorge feeding interspersed by days without hunting (Kleinlugtenbelt et al. 2023b). Used appropriately for a species, fasting days can be an important way of structuring time beyond the daily cycle for zoo carnivores and lead to a reduction in unwanted behaviours. Overall, these changes reflect a deeper understanding of the importance of nutrition, feeding behaviour, and enrichment in promoting big cats' health and welfare, thereby increasing their overall survival.

Changes in perception of the body condition

The perception of body condition in big cats within zoological institutions has evolved, now emphasising optimal body mass for physical health and longevity (Kleinlugtenbelt et al. 2023a). Appropriate diet changes have shown potential for increasing longevity in other species (e.g., pangolins, Wen Yang et al. 2007; humans, Ekmekcioglu 2020). During the 1980s and 1990s, big cats were often kept with higher body condition scores (i.e., obesity; Pers. Comm. from the Experts during the Species360 Experts workshop series, 2023). Over the past decade, there has been a shift towards a more streamlined appearance, reflecting a better understanding of diet management. A recent survey by Kleinlugtenbelt et al. (2023a) found no significant evidence of dramatic obesity among zoo carnivores and highlighted the importance of distinguishing between obesity and natural size variations. For example, **jaguars** in resource-rich habitats may appear robust due to higher food intake, a result of phenotypic plasticity rather than inherent biological tendencies (Hayward et al. 2016).

Understanding natural body size variations influenced by habitat resources helps refine target weights and manage health, wellbeing, and survival. The development of Feline Body Condition Guidelines marks a significant shift in assessing physical health. Several Body Condition Scoring systems exist for big cats, such as those for **lions** (AZA Lion Survival Plan 2012) and **jaguars** (AZA Jaguar Species Survival Plan 2016; Biddle 2022). For example, a multi-institutional effort for **lions** was published in 2015 the International Zoo Yearbook (Daigle et al. 2015).

Environment

The welfare conditions in which animals are housed influence their reproductive potential as well as their survival (Broom 1991; Walker et al. 2012). Indeed, captivity represents an evolutionarily novel

environment for wild animals, to which some species adapt readily, while others exhibit signs of stress, such as health, reproductive, and behavioural issues, if their needs are not adequately addressed (e.g., Mason 2010; Mellor et al. 2018; Bandeli et al. 2023).

Historical changes in big cats' exhibits

Over recent decades, zoological institutions worldwide have replaced small, barren enclosures with larger, naturalistic ones to better meet animals' behavioural and psychological needs. This evolution in zoo enclosure design reflects a significant shift from early misconceptions about *Panthera* species to a more empathetic and ecologically focused approach. Historically, restrictive enclosures lacking features to accommodate natural behaviours led to high stress and stereotypical behaviours in big cats, likely contributing to lower survival rates (Experts, Pers. Comm.; Figure 1).

By the 1880s, criticisms of bars and barren cages in North American zoos initiated a transition towards more naturalistic enclosures, marking the start of improvements in animal longevity. In the early 20th century, advancements in health and hygiene led to the development of facilities prioritising easy cleaning and durability, significantly increasing the longevity of *Panthera* species, despite neglecting their need for stimulation and choice (Coe 1996). By the mid-1970s, enclosures began to reflect natural habitats, offering opportunities for occupation and choice. The 1980s saw the construction of more spacious and diverse enclosures with natural substrates and enrichment items to stimulate curiosity, addressing the animals' needs comprehensively.

Accredited zoological institutions ensure enclosures meet both the physical and psychological needs of animals (Beer et al. 2023). The AZA Accreditation Standards (AZA, 2022) set minimum requirements for species management and care, including monitoring water and air quality, controlling sounds and vibrations, and minimising stress from human contact through concealed or distant viewing platforms (Tilson et al. 2016). Enclosure designs now consider the different adaptation times between sexes, with females typically requiring more time to adjust due to their philopatric nature in solitary species (Experts, Pers. Comm.). There is also growing recognition of the need to minimise stress from visitor interaction, leading to viewing areas that allow observation without causing undue stress.

Changes in enclosure size, complexity and opportunities

Throughout the last century, the enclosure size for *Panthera* species has progressively increased. For example, countries like Switzerland, Germany, Belgium, Great Britain, Northern Ireland, the USA, Sweden, and Australia have established laws specifying minimum space requirements (see Breton and Barrot 2014). Given their naturally itinerant lifestyles, big cats cover large distances in the wild, making them prone to pacing in captivity. However, studies on zoo **tigers** have shown that larger, naturalistic enclosures reduce pacing behaviour, increase distance covered, and improve space utilisation (Lyons et al. 1997; White et al. 2003; Bashaw et al. 2007; Szokalski et al. 2012; Breton and Barrot 2014). Similarly, a **leopard** study showed that complex environments foster natural behaviours and reduce stereotypic behaviours (Mallapur and Chellam 2002) (see also the section *Understanding stereotypical behaviour*).

The *quality* of space is as important as its *quantity*, therefore, modern exhibit design in accredited zoological institutions addresses the physical, social, behavioural, and psychological needs of species while managing group dynamics (e.g., Tilson et al. 2016; AZA 2022; Biddle 2022). This includes

designing open-air enclosures with natural substrates and vegetation to add environmental complexity. Modern facilities incorporate elements such as sunlight access, indoor/outdoor areas, and human interactions, to provide animals with choices and control, supporting positive emotional experiences (Dawkins 2004; Whitham and Miller 2016). Providing animals the opportunity to make choices that best suit their needs is crucial, including modifications to support ageing individuals, such as installing ramps for elderly animals to access elevated resting spots. Structures are ideally designed in a way that their arrangement can be changed repeatedly.

Changes in enrichment practices

Since the 1970s, researchers have recognized that captive environments significantly influence the development of animal behaviour and decrease stereotypic behaviours in carnivores (e.g., Mellen and Sevenich MacPhee 2001; Swaisgood and Shepherdson 2005). Even though behavioural enrichment only became mandatory in AZA-accredited facilities in 2000, incorporating features that promote natural behaviours, such as hidden items to encourage exploration and feeding behaviours goes beyond that (Tilson et al. 2016). Research on enrichment for big cats in zoological institutions has notably increased since the 1980s, with initial programs focusing on great apes and marine mammals through training initiatives. By the early 1990s, enrichment programs for big cats became more widespread (Law et al. 1997), reflecting a significant research effort within progressive zoological institutions (Podturkin and Papaeva 2020). Food-based enrichment mimicking hunting behaviour started in this period, focusing on social enrichment, while human-animal interaction as enrichment is more recent (Szokalski et al. 2012). Most efforts target natural feeding and hunting behaviours, with additional attention to olfactory stimulation and enclosure size. However, social housing and human contact remain less explored areas of enrichment.

Social management

Big cat species, except for **lions**, have traditionally been considered solitary and kept alone in enclosures. However, studies over the past few decades have shown that wild individuals of *Panthera* species regularly interact with conspecifics (Jackson 1996; Sunquist and Sunquist 2002; Miller and Kuhar 2008; Verschueren et al. 2023). Social context influences the welfare of big cats in zoological institutions, impacting their health, reproduction, survival, and longevity (Daigle et al. 2015). Providing an adequate social environment is essential to meet species and individual needs, as individual wellbeing influences health and longevity (Diener and Chan 2011; Weiss et al. 2011; Walker et al. 2012).

For example, although primarily solitary, **tigers** occasionally form temporary groups in the wild for activities like feeding, resting, and cooperative hunting, demonstrating their capacity for social behaviour (Miller and Kuhar 2008). Spatial recommendations for **tigers** in zoological institutions include provisions for separating and rotating individuals, including adults and cubs, to manage social interactions effectively (Tilson et al. 2016). Paired **tigers** exhibit significantly less pacing and a wider variety of behaviours compared to solitary **tigers**, particularly when not housed near other conspecifics (De Rouck et al. 2005).

Animal welfare

A focus on the animals' wellbeing

Species with large natural ranges, such as felids, face specific challenges under human care, often reflected in elevated infant mortality due to maternal stress and abnormal behaviour (Clubb and Mason 2007; Díez-León and Mason 2016). Therefore, accounting for individual needs by considering the species, age, sex and personality (Marieke Cassia and David 2012), is one of the goals of the accredited zoological institutions, leading to the increase in the population's life expectancy and lifespan equality.

Ensuring optimal welfare involves more than just veterinary care, safe environments, and proper nutrition; it also encompasses the individual animal's overall sum of daily positive and negative experiences (Webb et al. 2019). In several species, there is evidence that individual affective state influences health and therefore mortality and longevity (Walker et al. 2012), with happier individuals that have been shown to live longer in several species (Diener and Chan 2011; Weiss et al. 2011).

The concept of animal welfare gained prominence in the 1960s, initially focusing on intensive farming conditions (Veissier et al. 2008). Over time, its scope has expanded to include laboratory, companion, and zoo-housed animals (Webster 2005; Whitham and Wielebnowski 2009). While there is no single definition of animal welfare, it is generally accepted that welfare primarily concerns how the animal is *feeling* (Broom and Fraser 2015; Dawkins 2015) or how an individual is coping with the conditions in which it lives (Rose and O'Brien 2020; Jones et al. 2022). The study and perception of animal welfare in zoological institutions have evolved significantly, recognizing its crucial role in enhancing the health, reproduction, and longevity of captive animals (Broom 1991; Wielebnowski et al. 2002). Recent advances include the concepts of the *Five Domains* and *A Life Worth Living* (Green and Mellor 2011; Mellor et al. 2020), yet many welfare aspects remain to be addressed by both scientists and animal care professionals (Ward et al. 2018).

While foundational, this framework requires continual reassessment to encompass proactive welfare measures (McCulloch 2013). Therefore, from 2023, WAZA made welfare assessment plans mandatory from their member institutions (WAZA 2023). Ultimately, improving welfare in zoological institutions enhances reproductive potential and longevity, bolstering conservation, research, and education efforts.

Understanding stereotypical behaviour

Carnivores, especially wide-ranging species, often exhibit stereotypic behaviours like pacing in captivity (Clubb and Mason 2003). However, it is crucial to distinguish between stereotypic behaviours that are widely considered as a sign of substandard welfare when animals develop them, and the expression of natural movement patterns. For example, **tigers** in the wild travel extensively, which should not be misinterpreted as pacing in captivity (Breton and Barrot 2014).

Research has increasingly focused on understanding and mitigating these stereotypic behaviours (e.g., Mellor et al. 2018; Bandeli et al. 2023), which persist as coping mechanisms once developed and are, as in humans, challenging to eliminate without pharmacological intervention (Poulsen et al. 1996;

Swaisgood and Shepherdson 2005; Bauer et al. 2013). This complexity indicates that stereotypic behaviour may be initiated by either the current conditions of an animal's enclosure or its past experiences, making it difficult to identify the precise cause. Consequently, there is an increased effort to understand the aetiology of stereotypic behaviour, aiming to better anticipate its onset and improve the likelihood of eliminating it through enhanced housing and husbandry practices (Swaisgood and Shepherdson 2005; Mason et al. 2007). For instance, increasing the complexity of **leopards'** enclosure leads to more activity and less stereotypic pacing (Mallapur and Chellam 2002).

Finally, research in animal welfare is seeing a recent emphasis on individuals' personality as well as providing choice and control on its environment (Englund and Cronin 2023). For example, bold and captive-raised **Asiatic lions** exhibit fewer stereotypies compared to wild-rescued and shy ones (Goswami et al. 2020). Personality traits can influence how animals cope with their environment and therefore impact their health and reproductive success, and ultimately their survival (Phillips and Peck 2007; Marieke Cassia and David 2012; Gartner and Weiss 2013; Pastorino et al. 2017; Goswami et al. 2020).

Conclusion

This report empirically and statistically demonstrates the increase in a population-level welfare indicator based on survival summary metrics and discusses the different amelioration of living standards among the *Panthera* species within accredited zoological settings.

This report emphasises the advancements in husbandry and management practices for the five *Panthera* species – namely **lion** (*P. leo*), **jaguar** (*P. onca*), **leopard** (*P. pardus*), **tiger** (*P. tigris*) and **snow leopard** (*P. uncia*) – under human care that have been made by accredited zoological institutions over the past century. The efficacy of these improvements is made evident in the progressive and significant increase in life expectancy and lifespan equality of the populations of the five species living in zoological institutions. While the measure of a long life does not necessarily equate with a good (high-welfare) life, the use of longevity as a welfare indicator is intuitive: on the one hand, happier and healthier individuals live longer, as shown in humans and non-human primates (Diener and Chan 2011; Weiss et al. 2011). On the other hand, living conditions that accidentally induce premature death in a population cannot be reconciled with a high level of population welfare (Walker et al. 2012).

Panthera species, playing a pivotal role in the ecosystems they inhabit as apex predators, are increasingly threatened by human activities, including habitat destruction, poaching, and climate change (Estes et al. 2011; Ripple et al. 2014; Ceballos et al. 2015). As their numbers dwindle in the wild (IUCN 2023), zoological institutions have become crucial sanctuaries for the long-term survival and understanding of these species (Christie 2010; Conde et al. 2013; Hutchins et al. 2016). Accredited zoological institutions holding *Panthera* species are **(i)** key partners for species **conservation** such as by maintaining genetically diverse and healthy self-sustainable populations (IUCN SSC 2023), **(ii)** powerful **educational platforms** raising awareness about the plight of big cats and encouraging people to support conservation efforts and adopt more sustainable lifestyles that reduce human impact on the environment (Bruni et al. 2008; Conway 2011; Godinez and Fernandez 2019; McNally et al. 2024), and **(iii)** **centres for scientific research** that contributes to our understanding of big cats (Loh et al. 2018; Hvilsom et al. 2020; Kögler et al. 2020). Accredited institutions provide a sanctuary where these animals can thrive and serve as ambassadors for their wild counterparts. By participating in breeding programs, supporting field conservation efforts, educating the public, and conducting vital research, accredited zoological institutions also contribute significantly to the global efforts to save big cats from extinction.

As observed in modern human populations with increasing longevity, accredited zoological institutions face a similar challenge with the ageing of animals, leading to significant geriatric issues. The progressive increase in animal longevity necessitates a shift in focus from merely extending lifespan to enhancing the quality of life. Geriatric management is now a critical component of animal welfare, emphasising care at the end of life when animals are no longer in a good state. Veterinary practices have evolved, yet equating longevity with good welfare is increasingly scrutinised. Advances in veterinary care and rising public expectations have prompted zoological institutions to adopt more supportive therapies for aged animals (Nieuwland and Meijboom 2023). These interventions include pain management, nutritional adjustments, and habitat modifications to accommodate reduced mobility and other age-related challenges (Brando and Chapman 2023). The shift is supported by research focusing on the specific needs of ageing animal populations (Brando and Chapman 2023),

leading to specialised care plans that ensure older animals maintain a good quality of life. Public perception of geriatric management has also evolved, with greater acceptance and understanding of the need for humane end-of-life care (Chapman et al. 2023). However, differences between institutions persist, influenced by varying legal frameworks, public opinions, and institutional policies. Consequently, while some zoological institutions may strive to keep the oldest animals alive, others recognize that longevity alone is not necessarily indicative of good welfare, balancing the decision to humanely euthanize for population management reasons with the welfare of the individual and social group dynamics, and with the necessity to use the limited holding space for reproductively active members of the population to ensure that population's sustainability.

While improvements in life expectancy and lifespan equality reflect positive changes in the living conditions and overall welfare of big cat populations in modern zoological institutions, this metric alone cannot be used to assess individual welfare. Increasing the average lifespan indicates that, as a whole, the conditions are favourable for the species. However, it does not guarantee that every individual within the population is thriving under these improved conditions. Each animal's experience and personality are unique, and not all may cope equally well with the environment provided, challenging zoological institutions to adapt the management according to the individual needs. Therefore, while celebrating these advancements, it remains crucial to focus on the individual welfare of each animal to ensure that all are benefiting from the improved standards of care. To achieve this goal, rigorously capturing data on individual welfare, as done in the *Care & Welfare* module of ZIMS, is critical for enhancing not only the quantity but, more importantly, the quality of life of great apes in zoological institutions.

Ensuring the survival of these species requires a multifaceted approach, and accredited zoological institutions are at the forefront of this endeavour, bridging the gap between the wild and human society in the quest to preserve our planet's biodiversity.

List of acronyms

AAZV:	American Association of Zoo Veterinarians (1946)
ACZM:	American College of Zoological Medicine
ALPZA:	Latin American Zoo and Aquarium Association (1990)
AWA:	Animal Welfare Act of 1966 in the US
AZA:	(North American) Association of Zoo and Aquariums (1924)
BaSTA	Bayesian Survival Trajectory Analysis
BCSA:	Big Cat Sanctuary Alliance
BVZS:	British Veterinary Zoological Society (1961)
CKD:	Chronic Kidney Disease
CITES:	Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (1975)
CZAI:	The Central Zoo Authority of India
EAZA:	European Association of Zoos and Aquaria (previously ECAZA, 1985)
EAZWV:	European Association of Zoo and Wildlife Veterinarians (1996)
ECZM:	European College of Zoological Medicine
EEP:	EAZA Ex-situ Programme (previously European Endangered Species Programme)
IUCN:	International Union for Conservation of Nature
PAAZA:	Pan-African Association of Zoo and Aquaria (1989)
SEAZA:	SouthEast Asian Zoos and Aquariums Association (1990)
SMP:	Species Management Program (ZAA)
SSC:	Species Survival Commission (IUCN)
SSP:	Species Survival Plan (AZA)
TAG:	Taxon Advisory Group
UK:	United Kingdom
USA:	United States of America
WAWV:	World Association of Wildlife Veterinarians (1991)
WAZA:	World Association of Zoos and Aquariums (1935)
ZAA:	Zoo and Aquarium Association Australasia (1990)
ZIMS:	Zoological Information Management System (Species360)

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